

Dimethylaminohydroxyphenoxazone Carboxylic Acid as an Indicator in Complexometric Determination of Thorium

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Use of dimethylaminohydroxyphenoxazone carboxylic acid (gallocyanine) as an indicator in the complexometric determination of thorium with EDTA has been described. The use of 0.03 c.c. of indicator solution (0.02% in 5% Na_2CO_3 and neutralised to pH 7.0) in each titration has been recommended. Sharp end points are observed up to a dilution of 0.0033*M* thorium chloride. The titrations are possible in the temperature range of 0°-100°, but pH must be adjusted between 2.0 and 2.7. Several added foreign ions are found to interfere, but there is no interference from lithium, sodium, potassium, silver, calcium, strontium, barium, zinc, mercury, lead, and manganese ions.

Dimethylaminohydroxyphenoxazone carboxylic acid (gallocyanine) has found application in the detection of lead (Poole, B.D.H. *Book of Spot Tests*). Pavelka (*Mikrochem.*, 1930, 2, 345) reported characteristic colour reactions with several metals including thorium. Pavelka and Heisnar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 66, 340) also observed that the lakes with metals did not form definite stoichiometric compounds. Work in progress in these laboratories shows that gallocyanine forms coloured chelates with several metals and that the thorium chelate is violet in colour with λ_{max} 545 m μ at pH 1.5.

Sangal and Dey (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1961, in press) have reported the use of Chromeazurol S as a metal indicator in the complexometric determination of thorium. The present paper records our observations on gallocyanine as a suitable indicator for complexometric titrations of Th-EDTA.

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of BDH-AnalaR grade thorium chloride was prepared and standardised by precipitating thorium as oxalate in a 4% solution of HCl. It was ignited at 800° and weighed as ThO_2 . An exact solution of 0.1*M* was prepared by suitable dilution.

A 0.02% solution of gallocyanine was prepared by dissolving 0.1 g. of the dye (BDH spot test reagent) in a 5% aqueous solution of Na_2CO_3 . The volume was made to 500 c.c. after adjusting the pH of the solution to 7.0.

A 0.1*M*-EDTA solution was prepared by dissolving 18.6126 g. of its disodium salt in 500 c.c. and the concentration was checked against a primary standard solution of calcium chloride according to Goetz *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 222).

Foreign Ions.—0.1*M* solutions of the various reagents were prepared either by direct weighing or by standardising the solutions by the usual methods. Reagent grade chemicals were used.

A microburette with a least count of 0.02 c.c. was used for measuring the solutions. pH measurements were done by using a stabilised L & N pH indicator operated on 220V/50 cycles A.C. mains with a glass—calomel electrode system, supplied by the same manufacturer.

Concentration of the Indicator.—In the titration the end point may be detected by the change in colour from blue to pink when EDTA is added to the thorium chloride solution. The effect of concentration of the dye on the end point is of great importance, as with the change of its concentration the end point is slightly shifted. Accurate results with sharp end points are obtained by using 0.30 c.c. of the indicator solution for each titration.

Limit of Dilution.—Titrations were carried out with the solutions of different molarity and the titrations of thorium against EDTA were possible up to 0.0033M solutions; on further dilution the end point was not very sharp.

Effects of Temperature and pH.—Temperature effect between 0° and 100° was negligible. Titrations were carried out at different pH values of the thorium chloride solution. It may be seen that the pH of thorium solution suitable for titration is 2.0 to 2.7 (Table I).

TABLE I

Effect of pH.

0.02M-EDTA required = 10 c.c. Thorium taken = 0.0464 g.

pH	1.4	1.6	2.0	2.35	2.7	2.9	3.0	3.3
EDTA (c.c.)	No sharp end point	10.06	10.02	10.00	10.00	9.40	9.00	No sharp end point

Procedure.—A known quantity of thorium chloride solution was taken in a 250 c.c. Erlenmeyer flask; the pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.7 and 0.3 c.c. of indicator solution was added. The solution was now titrated against a standard EDTA solution with constant shaking until a distinct change of colour from blue to pink took place. Thorium present in the solution was determined from $\text{g. Th} = 0.2321 \times V \times M$ (where V is the volume and M is the molarity of the EDTA solution).

In order to compare the results and examine the suitability of the indicator, titrations with known solutions were carried out. Typical results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Thorium	Taken (mg.)	0.0928	0.0348	0.0232	0.0580	0.0696	0.0464	0.0812
	Found (mg.)	0.0927	0.0347	0.0231	0.0580	0.0695	0.0464	0.0811
	Diff	-0.0001	-0.0001	-0.0001	Nil	-0.0001	Nil	-0.0001

Interference due to Foreign Ions.—Presence of foreign ions caused interferences in the titrations due to the formation of stable versene complexes by the cations present, or a coloured complex with the indicator, or precipitates in certain cases. For noting the interference, titrations were carried out using 5 c.c. of 0.02M thorium chloride in presence of equimolar amounts of various cations and anions directly against EDTA

The observation show (the detailed titre values have been omitted to economise space) that the following anions and cations interfere: tartrate, oxalate, acetate, citrate, tetraborate, phosphate, fluoride, Cu(II), Au (III), Be(II), Mg (II), Cd(II), Al(III), Ti (IV), Zr(IV), Sn (IV), V (V), As(III), Sb (III), Bi (III), Cr (VI), Mo(VI), W (VI), Fe (III and II), Co (II), Ni (II), Ce (IV), and uranyl (II). On the other hand, the alkali and alkaline earth metals, silver (I), zinc (II), Hg (II), Pb (II), and Mn (II) do not interfere. Further work on the elimination of interfering ions in these titrations is in progress.

The authors thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the grant of a research fellowship to one of them (S.P.S.).